

Representación integral de las $e^{\alpha x} x^k y^l$ – funciones de onda

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Dedicated to Prof. Shyam Kalla
On the occasion of his 76th Anniversary

Recibido: 04-09-2013 Aceptado: 01-10-2013

Resumen

El trabajo trata con una nueva generalización de funciones analíticas. Se deducen algunas representaciones integrales de las $e^{\alpha x} x^k y^l$ - funciones de onda ($k, l, \alpha - const, > 0$) y sus fórmulas de inversión. Como una aplicación de la teoría se formulan dos problemas y se resuelven estos en forma cerrada.

Palabras clave: Funciones analíticas, funciones de onda.

Integral representation of $e^{\alpha x} x^k y^l$ – wave functions

Abstract

The paper deals with a new generalization of analytical functions. Some integral representations of $e^{\alpha x} x^k y^l$ - wave functions ($k, l, \alpha - const, > 0$), their inversion formulas are derived. As an application of the theory two problems are formulated and solved in the closed form.

Key words: Analytical functions, wave functions.

Introduction

The generalized analytical functions of complex variables appear as a natural and rational generalization of analytical functions.

Picard [1], Beltrami [2], Vekya [3,4], Polozij [5], Manjavidze [6], and others have obtained many important results in the generalization of the theory of analytical functions of elliptic type and their applications. For example, Polozij [5] introduced the analytical functions, using the system:

$$\begin{cases} pu_x - qu_y - v_y = 0, \\ qu_x + pu_y + v_x = 0, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where p and q are the given real functions of x and y .